

Summary of Workshop Integration Phase - Challenges and proposed Solutions

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In a virtual workshop on 16 February 2024, consortia-speakers and other representatives discussed what a commitment to support basic-service development means in real terms for the consortia. The workshop took place against the backdrop of a first basic service candidate, IAM4NFDI, now being in Base4NFDI's integration phase. This document summarises one premise, three key challenges identified, and solutions proposed.

Graphical Summary:

Premise

Premise regarding the role of consortia:

- Base4NFDI is a common endeavor by all NFDI consortia. As such the NFDI community works together for its success and makes efforts to integrate, adopt,

and use the basic services. Base4NFDI supports and helps consortia to integrate long-term, sustainable basic services.

Challenges and proposed Solutions

Challenge 1: Consortia need clarification of what *commitment to a service* means in practical terms

- Base4NFDI **extends the Consortia Survey with questions** and adds a clarifying paragraph on the integration of a basic service to help consider pathways to commitment when consortia decide to vote for the service.
- Add a “**Stakeholder Matrix**” as a deliverable during the initialisation phase to help formalise the contacts that develop over time, to avoid repetitive outreach to the consortia, and to create easy-to-reach and fixed communication channels.
- Consortia identify a point of contact (“**Service Advocates**”) per consortium to facilitate communication between consortia and basic service teams and to forward future pathways for integrating a service.

Challenge 2: Consortia require more information (technical specifications, outlook, benefits, etc.) about of a service in the integration stage

- Base4NFDI will host a public **Submissions Webinar** per submission timeframe (integration and ramping-up phase) for consortia to help understand the scope of each basic service.
- Base4NFDI will hold **monthly meetings with basic service teams**, a touch point to follow technical developments and address any challenges.
- Base4NFDI will facilitate **Community Workshops** for each integration stage of a basic service at regular intervals to address technical issues.
- **Service Fact Sheets** will be produced by the basic service teams for the integration phase with Base4NFDI’s support to show an overview of the service description, commitment, and resources needed.
- Base4NFDI will **engage with consortia at consortia events** (conferences, workshops, etc.) to understand the structure, background and strategy of each consortium.

Challenge 3: Consortia need time and resources to put into action practical steps of a service integration

- Base4NFDI facilitates a **strategy meeting** in 05/2024 with consortia representatives to agree on a text to insert into the consortias’ prolongation proposals that clarifies the efforts needed to integrate a service (resources, expertise).
- Base4NFDI will initiate a **targeted dialogue** with consortia individually to invite consortia to systematically evaluate the current and upcoming consortia strategy with regards to our premise and help them form ideas on how to integrate a service. Promote the concept of running **incubator pilots (targeted development**

cycle for integration in the basic service) during integration phase has been proven successfully.